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Microstructural evolution and mechanical response of ion-irradiated Fe-9Cr alloys: Insights from nanoindentation

K. Mulewska^{a,*} , Ł. Kurpaska^a

^a NOMATEN Centre of Excellence, National Centre for Nuclear Research, ul. A. Soltana 7, 05 400 Otwock, Poland

^b Warsaw University of Technology, Faculty of Materials Science and Engineering, st. Woloska 141, 02-507 Warsaw, Poland

^c Advanced Materials for Nuclear Energy, VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, Kivimiehentie 3, Espoo 02150, Finland

HIGHLIGHTS

- Smaller indenters measure higher shear stress than larger spherical ones.
- RT irradiation increases loop density, strengthening and hardening the material.
- Dense loops from RT irradiation raise critical stress, hindering dislocation motion.
- At 300 °C, loops near dislocations enable channels, easing dislocation glide.

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the mechanical behavior of Fe-Cr alloys under irradiation is crucial for their application in nuclear environments. This study investigates the evolution of dislocation structures and their impact on the nanoindentation response of Fe-9Cr alloys in five distinct conditions: (1) non-irradiated pristine material, (2) non-irradiated material annealed at 300 °C, (3) material irradiated with 10 MeV Fe²⁺ ions to 5 dpa at room temperature, (4) material irradiated with 10 MeV Fe²⁺ ions to 1 dpa at 300 °C, and (5) material irradiated with 10 MeV Fe²⁺ ions to 5 dpa at 300 °C. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis revealed that irradiation at RT leads to a dense distribution of dislocation loops, which act as strong obstacles to dislocation glide, significantly increasing the critical stress required for plastic deformation. In contrast, irradiation at 300 °C results in a lower density of defects in the matrix, with dislocation loops observed near pre-existing dislocation lines. This defect configuration facilitates the formation of dislocation channels, reducing overall obstruction to dislocation motion and leading to a decrease in pop-in stress compared to RT-irradiated samples. However, despite the apparent increase in dislocation mobility, Cr-decorated dislocation loops in the 300 °C-irradiated sample act as pinning sites, impeding the contribution of pre-existing dislocations to plastic deformation and necessitating the nucleation of new dislocations. Recorded mechanical properties, together with microstructural evolution, provide critical insights into the mechanical response of Fe-Cr alloys, offering valuable implications for their performance in nuclear applications.

1. Introduction

In response to climate change, societies must transition to sustainable energy sources. Although nuclear power plants have been in use for decades, ongoing efforts to enhance their efficiency continue to drive advancements in this field. Ferritic/martensitic (F/M) steels are prime candidates for the structural components of Generation IV fission and

fusion reactors due to their excellent properties, such as high thermal conductivity, low thermal expansion, and reduced helium embrittlement [1–6]. However, F/M steels tend to harden significantly when exposed to radiation at around 300 °C, the typical operating temperature for most nuclear reactors. Additionally, transient and localized temperature fluctuations are inevitable depending on the reactor component and cooling method. This hardening is accelerated by the

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Katarzyna.Mulewska@ncbj.gov.pl (K. Mulewska).

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formation of radiation defects that obstruct dislocation movement, resulting in decreased fracture toughness and a notable reduction in uniform elongation. Despite considerable experimental and numerical efforts, the mechanism of radiation damage accumulation and its impact on the material's plasticity remain poorly understood, especially for complex systems such as Eurofer 97 (EU97). To address this, our work progresses by increasing structural complexity to isolate specific features and mechanisms associated with each level of structural enhancement. In our previous study, we focused on a model Fe system [7,8], while in this study, we investigate the Fe-Cr model material.

Radiation-induced defect types in F/M steels, occurring during irradiation include the creation of vacancies and interstitials which cause hardening and embrittlement [1]. Agglomeration of vacancies may lead to void swelling leading to dimensional instability [9,10]. Finally, one cannot omit radiation-induced segregation of alloying elements at grain boundaries, which can be detrimental to the mechanical properties as a result of intergranular embrittlement [4]. Furthermore, transmutation reactions generate helium and hydrogen, increasing susceptibility to cracking [1,4], while long-term phase instability and precipitate evolution alter the steel's microstructure [4]. For a comprehensive understanding of radiation-induced hardening, the interaction between microstructural features and defects is crucial for optimizing F/M steels for next-generation nuclear applications.

Radiation-induced defects are generated through neutron interaction with the material originating from the reactor core. However, these defects can also be generated via ion irradiation by using an ion accelerator facility [10]. Ion irradiation is particularly attractive because it allows for controlled displacement damage under well-defined time and temperature conditions. Over the past decades, it has been shown that this technique can successfully replicate all the microstructural features observed in neutron-irradiated materials, such as dislocation loops, voids, bubbles, and radiation-induced solute segregation [11–17]. This method allows for the reproduction of reactor conditions, providing greater experimental control and facilitating the study of specific phenomena, such as the impact of radiation-induced defects on dislocation nucleation and evolution [18]. Additionally, ion irradiation does not activate the sample, simplifying and reducing the cost of specimen handling. However, this methodology has a few burdens, for example, the damage region created by ions is usually confined to a few micrometers, even with high-energy ions. Therefore, specialized techniques focused on probing small material volumes are needed to investigate their mechanical, structural, and thermal properties.

It is known that ion irradiation at room temperature provides a controlled environment for studying irradiation effects without thermally induced phenomena, serving as a baseline for comparison. Under these conditions, defects such as vacancies, interstitials, and dislocation loops have limited mobility and tend to accumulate, leading to distinct microstructural changes. In contrast, at elevated temperatures, increased atomic mobility enhances defect migration, recombination, and clustering, resulting in dynamic annealing, a process in which certain defects are healed or reduced in real time. This interplay between irradiation and thermal effects can drive unique mechanisms such as radiation-enhanced diffusion, significantly affecting phase stability and precipitation kinetics. Unlike room-temperature irradiation, where defects persist and accumulate, high-temperature irradiation alters the microstructure through defect interactions that ultimately shape the material's long-term stability. Given the operational conditions in nuclear reactors (periodic shut-down of the reactor required for refuelling), understanding defect accumulation processes in the whole temperature range is essential for predicting and improving material performance [19,20].

Nanoindentation has become an essential method in recent years for assessing the mechanical properties of ion-irradiated materials, including hardness and Young's modulus [7,13,21–27]. While most studies focus on using a single type of indenter, such as the Berkovich tip, our research investigates the use of various indenters to gain a

deeper understanding of material behavior and observed phenomena. A sharp indenter, with its smaller radius of curvature, creates a higher stress concentration at the tip when contacting the material surface [28, 29]. This concentrated stress can lead to local plastic deformation or even fracture. As the applied load increases, the stress at the indenter tip intensifies, making it more likely to exceed the material's yield strength and cause a pop-in event. The sharp tip, with its greater stress concentration, makes the material more prone to sudden displacement. In contrast, a larger indenter contacts a broader area of the material, leading to a more extensive deformation field. This larger contact area results in a higher volume of material undergoing plastic deformation, which also increases the likelihood of a pop-in. Additionally, the larger indenter generates higher localized stresses, especially at the edges of the contact region, further raising the probability of pop-in. While both sharp and large indenters increase the likelihood of pop-in, they each have specific advantages in testing. A sharp indenter provides better spatial resolution, allowing for the study of localized properties, such as grain boundaries or small-scale features [30–33]. On the other hand, a larger indenter averages out local inhomogeneities, providing a more accurate representation of the bulk material's properties [28,32,33].

The pop-in phenomenon can have various origins, including crack nucleation and propagation or phase transitions [30,32,34]. The magnitude of the pop-in and the stress required to trigger the elastic-to-plastic transition depend on the material's structural features, such as grain boundaries, precipitates, or point defects that may block dislocation movement. Nanoindentation can be used to investigate the plasticity of the ion-irradiated material, as it allows the probe of small volumes, revealing the mechanical behavior of the studied system. Enriched with structural data, it builds a complete set of information necessary to understand impact of radiation induced defects via ion irradiation.

In this work, we systematically investigated the deformation behavior of a Fe-9Cr model alloy using nanoindentation under various conditions: irradiation temperature (room temperature and 300 °C), damage level (pristine, 1 dpa, and 5 dpa), and the combination of temperature and damage level (5 dpa at room temperature and 5 dpa at 300 °C). This allowed us to build a comprehensive database on the behavior of the Fe-9Cr model alloy under conditions representative of those in a pressurized water reactor (PWR). Recorded nanoindentation revealed the dose-dependent behavior of dislocation nucleation and propagation in the irradiated regions of the material, offering insights into the early-stage deformation behaviour of the irradiated Fe-9Cr model alloy. By employing indenter tips with different effective radii, we distinguished between dislocation nucleation and propagation in these measurements. Such insights are crucial for designing and predicting the performance of structural components in future reactors.

2. Experimental and computational methods

2.1. Material

The material under investigation is a binary Fe-9Cr model alloy produced by OCAS (Ghent, Belgium). The chemical composition is listed in Table 1. The material displayed a ferritic microstructure with an average grain size of approx. $35 \pm 14 \mu\text{m}$ with some bainitic structures (marked with yellow arrows in Fig. 1), constituting approximately 10 % of the investigated area. A visual representation of the microstructure, captured through an inverse pole figure (IPF) map using electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD), is presented in Fig. 1. It's essential to note that all subsequent investigations detailed in this study are focused

Table 1
Chemical composition of the Fe-9Cr samples.

Element	C	N	Si	P	Ni	Cr	Fe
Weight (%)	<0.006	<0.005	0.004	0.003	0.009	9.1	Bal.

Fig. 1. EBSD map of IPF Z z-axis orientations of non-irradiated Fe-9Cr annealed at 300 °C for 8 hours. The bainitic structure is marked with yellow arrows.

on the ferritic matrix. To ensure high-quality EBSD measurements, the sample surface was initially ground with silicone carbide sandpapers (up to 2500 grit) and subsequently electro-polished. The electro-polishing process was conducted using a solution composed of 60 mL perchloric acid and 940 mL ethanol, at a temperature of 10 °C, under a voltage of 27 V for 45 seconds. EBSD data were acquired using an EDAX Velocity Pro EBSD camera under the following beam conditions: an accelerating voltage of 25 kV and a beam current of 6.4 nA. The scanning was performed with a step size of 0.8 µm, with α -ferrite selected as the reference phase. Data acquisition was carried out using EDAX APEX 2.2 software, and subsequent data processing was performed using OIM Analysis 8.6. The average grain size was determined from the EBSD maps by calculating the equivalent diameter, employing the “grain size (diameter)” procedure. No data cleaning procedures were applied, and all EBSD maps presented are raw, unprocessed maps.

2.2. Ion irradiation

The ion irradiation experiment took place at the Ion Beam Center within the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR) research laboratory, utilizing a 3 MV tandemron accelerator. Fe²⁺ ions with 10 MeV energy were used to irradiate the sample at room temperature up to 5 dpa (displacements per atom) and at 300 °C up to 1 and 5 dpa at the peak damage. The selected damage levels of 1 dpa and 5 dpa were chosen to simulate conditions representative of the service life of structural components made from ferritic/martensitic (F/M) steels, particularly in fusion and advanced fission reactor environments. These dose levels correspond to the expected exposure range for components located in the core periphery or in moderately irradiated structural regions over operational timescales. Previous studies on ex-service F/M steels [1,3,4], such as those from sodium-cooled fast reactors and fusion-relevant irradiation campaigns, often report microstructural changes and property degradations within this dpa range. By selecting 1 and 5 dpa, we aimed to capture both the early/moderate-stage damage evolution (1 dpa) and more advanced degradation behavior (5 dpa), enabling a broader understanding of material performance under realistic irradiation conditions.

A thermo-couple was employed to monitor the temperature on the backsides of the samples while the samples themselves were mounted on a heating target. The ion beam was precisely focused to guarantee uniform exposure across the irradiated area. The ion flux was continuously monitored to obtain the required fluence. The profiles of displacements

per atom (dpa) and injected interstitials (ipa) were calculated using the SRIM (Stopping and Range of Ions in Matter) binary collision code [35, 36] with a threshold displacement energy of 40 eV [37]. The dpa and ipa profiles are displayed in Fig. 2 with the STEM image of the irradiated sample in the background to visualize the material damage better.

2.3. Nanoindentation technique

Nanomechanical investigations were conducted using the NanoTest Vantage system provided by Micro Materials Ltd. The measurements were carried out at room temperature utilizing different diamond indenter tips. Indentations were performed in single force mode, applying a maximum load of 1.5 mN for the Berkovich tip and 15 mN for the spherical indenter tip with a tip radius of 5 µm.

These loads were selected to probe mechanical behavior at different length scales within the irradiation-affected region. The lower load of 1.5 mN enabled the investigation of localized responses, such as dislocation nucleation and interactions with irradiation-induced defects, whereas the higher load of 15 mN sampled a larger volume, capturing more representative, volume-averaged mechanical properties of the irradiated microstructure as a whole.

For the Berkovich indenter, the loading rate was set to 0.3 mN/s, followed by a 2 s hold at maximum load and an unloading rate of 0.5 mN/s. In the case of the spherical tip, a loading rate of 1 mN/s was used, with a 5 s hold at peak load and an unloading rate of 3 mN/s. To account for thermal drift, a 60 s hold segment was included during unloading at 10 % of the maximum load; this post-indentation drift correction was applied to all datasets. Each load condition was repeated at least 200 times on both pristine and irradiated specimens. Prior to testing, the diamond area function (DAF) for each indenter was calibrated using fused silica with known mechanical properties.

2.4. Microstructure characterization (SEM/TEM)

Structural observations were conducted using a Helios 5 UX scanning electron microscope (SEM) from ThermoFisher Scientific. Electron-transparent lamellae of both pristine and ion-irradiated Fe-9Cr material were prepared utilizing the Focused Ion Beam (FIB) lift-out technique. The thinning process was carried out with progressively decreasing beam acceleration, to minimize the impact of Ga ions on the dislocation structures. Two FIB lamellae, irradiated to a dose of 5 dpa at room temperature and 300 °C, were further processed through flash polishing. The polishing process employed a 3 % concentration of

Fig. 2. Profiles of displacement damage (red line) and concentration of injected interstitials (blue line) for the 10MeV Fe²⁺ ion irradiation obtained by SRIM calculations superimposed on the STEM image.

Struers A3 solution as the electrolyte. Electropolishing was performed for 300 ms at 30 V and 16.67 Hz, using a squared waveform at a temperature of $-60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. General observations of the lamellae were conducted in Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) mode, followed by a detailed analysis using a JEOL JEM F200 Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) operated at 200 kV. The TEM samples for the analysis of the deformed zone, beneath the indenter tip, were prepared from indents made in grains oriented close to $\{011\}$, parallel to the surface.

3. Results

3.1. Nanoindentation

Our study focuses on visualizing the pop-in phenomena and establishing a correlation between the length of the pop-in event and the critical load. The occurrence of pop-ins signifies the onset of plasticity and may result from either the nucleation of new dislocations or the mobilization of pre-existing dislocations. These distinct mechanisms can be differentiated by employing indenter tips with varying radii.

Fig. 3 displays load-displacement (L-D) curves obtained from nanoindentation tests using a Berkovich tip (see Fig. 3a), and with a spherical indenter tip with a nominal radius of $5\ \mu\text{m}$ (see Fig. 3b). The curves represent specimens under different conditions: pristine at room temperature (RT) black line, pristine annealed at $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ red line, ion irradiated at RT up to 5 dpa green, 1 dpa at $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ blue, and 5 dpa at $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ violet. The average maximum depth reached by all indents is shown in Table 2. Before the occurrence of the pop-in effect, it is evident that the shape of the load-displacement curves is identical for all specimens. This observation confirms that samples possess the same density of

Table 2

Maximum depth recorded during nanoindentation on Fe-9Cr model alloy samples.

Sample	Average max. depth (nm)				
	pristine	Pristine annealed	5dpa	1dpa	5dpa
Tip	RT	$300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	RT	$300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	$300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
Berkovich	163 ± 7	150 ± 9	136 ± 5	144 ± 8	135 ± 6
5 μm tip	305 ± 40	353 ± 43	288	330 ± 31	276 ± 25

dislocations and a similar number of pre-existing mobile dislocations. Moreover, the investigated surface exhibits no discontinuities related to the polishing procedure and demonstrates similar residual stress levels after polishing. This enables us to quantify and isolate the contribution of radiation damage to the hardening effect. Our previous studies on high-purity iron, such as those employing a Berkovich tip [7] and a spherical tip [8], have supported this assertion.

The specific load for Berkovich was carefully selected to ensure that the probed volume remained confined within the irradiated region, adhering to the most conservative 1/10 rule to minimize the potential influence of regions with peak damage [38]. As illustrated in Fig. 4, the damage distribution across the sample surface is relatively flat at a depth of around $1\ \mu\text{m}$. This uniform damage profile is expected to result in a uniform response to indentation. At these shallow indentation depths, the interaction between the Berkovich tip and the material primarily involves the irradiated layer, meaning the measured mechanical properties largely reflect the characteristics of this surface-damaged region.

Figs. 5 and Fig. 6 illustrate the correlation between critical load and

Fig. 3. Experimentally recorded load-displacement curves for: a) Berkovich tip, b) zoom-in on a pop-in made by the Berkovich tip, c) $5\ \mu\text{m}$ indenter, and d) zoom-in on pop-ins made by spherical tips. The curves correspond to the Fe-9Cr model alloy under different conditions: pristine at room temperature (black line), pristine annealed at $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (red line), ion-irradiated up to 5 dpa at RT (green line), 1 dpa at $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (blue line), and 5 dpa at $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (violet line).

Fig. 4. Schematic view of the nanoindentation process and damage distribution, with the damage-depth profile superimposed on the STEM image.

pop-in length for all pristine and ion-irradiated samples recorded by different indenter tips. The slight scattering of results can be attributed to variations in the crystallographic orientations of the probed grains, although the study did not specifically focus on the influence of this or grain boundary effects. Our study aims to visualize the pop-in phenomena and establish a correlation between the length of the pop-in event, the critical load, the indenter size and ion irradiation dose, and the temperature.

Observing the pristine state of the material at room temperature (black points) and annealed at 300 °C (red points) made with Berkovich indenter (Fig. 5a) and spherical indenter tip (Fig. 6a), it is evident that the critical load required to observe a pop-in event is lower for the annealed sample. This is because defects created during preparation tend to disappear at elevated temperatures. Specifically, the disappearance of these defects at elevated temperatures is likely due to

increased atomic mobility and enhanced defect diffusion, which aids in the healing or elimination of defects within the material [39].

In Fig. 5b, it is noticeable that the behavior of irradiated materials varies notably with the damage per atom level. Considering the dose level, it is clearly seen that samples irradiated up to 1 dpa require a lower critical load to observe a pop-in event than those irradiated up to 5 dpa at 300 °C. As the irradiation dose increases, the material experiences more severe defect accumulation, greater changes in mechanical properties (irradiation hardening), and more pronounced microstructural alterations. These differences underscore the importance of understanding and managing radiation damage in materials used in high-radiation environments [40,41].

Specifically, materials irradiated up to 5 dpa at room temperature (green points) and at 300 °C (violet points) exhibit distinct behaviors (Fig. 5c). Samples irradiated at higher temperatures require a lower critical load to observe a pop-in event. At room temperature, the low atomic mobility results in defects such as vacancies, interstitials, and dislocation loops accumulating and remaining largely immobile, leading to higher concentrations of defects. In contrast, higher temperatures increase atomic mobility, allowing defects to migrate and recombine more readily. This self-annealing effect reduces overall defect density. Radiation-induced damage is more severe at lower temperatures due to insufficient thermal energy for defect migration and recombination, resulting in higher residual stress. Conversely, materials irradiated at high temperatures often exhibit greater radiation tolerance, with enhanced defect recombination and annihilation processes leading to a more stable microstructure and improved performance in irradiated environments [42,43].

Differentiating dislocation nucleation and propagation can be achieved using various indenters. Fig. 6 illustrates the correlation of pop-in events using 5 μm spherical indenter tip. Varying the radii of indenter tips creates stress zones of different sizes beneath the surface. By changing the indenter radius, the size of the highly stressed zone in the material adjusts relative to the average dislocation spacing. If the radius of the spherical indenter is much smaller than the average spacing between dislocations, the likelihood of encountering a pre-existing dislocation in the highly stressed zone is low.

Consequently, for plastic deformation to occur, the applied stress must be high enough to nucleate a new dislocation. Conversely, if the indenter radius is much larger than the dislocation spacing, pre-existing dislocations will probably be present in the stressed zone. These dislocations can move at lower applied stresses than the stress needed to nucleate new dislocations.

Comparison of irradiation doses at 300 °C (Fig. 6b) indicates that samples irradiated up to 1 dpa exhibit mechanical behavior similar to pristine materials, requiring higher critical loads to observe pop-in events than samples irradiated up to 5 dpa. At lower displacements per atom (dpa), defects are sparsely distributed and exert minimal

Fig. 5. Linear correlation between the pop-in critical load and the pop-in length measured by nanoindentation with a Berkovich tip for Fe-9Cr alloys under different conditions: a) pristine material at room temperature (black) and after annealing at 300 °C (red); b) annealed at 300 °C (red), ion-irradiated to 1 dpa at 300 °C (blue), and to 5 dpa at 300 °C (violet); c) ion-irradiated to 5 dpa at room temperature (green) and at 300 °C (violet).

Fig. 6. Linear correlation between the pop-in critical load and the pop-in length measured by nanoindentation with a 5 μm spherical tip for Fe-9Cr alloys under different conditions: a) pristine material at room temperature (black) and after annealing at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (red); b) annealed at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (red), ion-irradiated to 1 dpa at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (blue), and to 5 dpa at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (violet); c) ion-irradiated to 5 dpa at room temperature (green) and at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (violet).

influence on the material's mechanical properties. However, as the irradiation dose increases, the prevalence of defect clusters and loops rises, enhancing the likelihood of interactions that significantly affect mechanical behavior. When comparing samples irradiated up to 5 dpa at different temperatures (Fig. 6c), those irradiated at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ necessitate higher critical loads than those irradiated at room temperature (RT). This is attributed to elevated temperature irradiation inducing significant microstructural transformations, such as the formation of dislocation loops, and the segregation of solute atoms to defects, all collectively altering the material's mechanical properties [44]. The increased temperature accelerates dislocation generation and mobility, with dislocations potentially becoming decorated by chromium, thus increasing dislocation density. Consequently, a higher density of defects must be mobilized or interacted with before a pop-in event can occur, necessitating higher stress levels to overcome this enhanced resistance.

The slope of the initial portion of the load–displacement curves obtained from nanoindentation testing, summarized in Table 3, provides an indirect measure of the near-surface stiffness and elastic response of the material under different irradiation and thermal histories. In the pristine condition at room temperature, the highest slopes were observed for both the Berkovich (191 mN/nm, $R^2 = 0.99$) and 5 μm spherical (19 mN/nm, $R^2 = 0.96$) indenters, reflecting the undegraded crystalline structure and absence of irradiation-induced defects. A pronounced reduction in slope was recorded in the sample irradiated to 5 dpa at room temperature, with values decreasing to 91 mN/nm (Berkovich) and 5 mN/nm (spherical), accompanied by a noticeable drop in linearity ($R^2 < 0.9$), indicating significant radiation-induced defect accumulation and associated degradation of the material's elastic stiffness. This is consistent with the formation of a high density of defect clusters, including interstitial-type dislocation loops and vacancy-rich regions, which disrupt the local elastic response.

In contrast, the sample irradiated to 1 dpa at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ exhibited substantially higher slope values (152 mN/nm for Berkovich, 15 mN/nm for spherical), approaching those of the unirradiated state. This suggests that irradiation at elevated temperature promotes dynamic recovery processes, including defect recombination and enhanced point defect

Table 3

Summary of the slopes (mN/nm) and correlation coefficients (R^2) obtained from the linear fitting of the unloading segment of load–displacement curves for Berkovich and 5 μm spherical indenters across different irradiation and temperature conditions.

Sample	Berkovich		5 μm	
	slope (mN/nm)	R^2	slope (mN/nm)	R^2
pristine RT	191	0.99	19	0.96
pristine 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	158	0.96	16	0.91
5 dpa RT	91	0.88	5	0.78
1 dpa 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	152	0.92	15	0.95
5 dpa 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	132	0.91	6	0.78

mobility, which mitigate the stiffening or softening effects typically observed at lower irradiation temperatures. A moderate recovery effect is also evident in the 5 dpa sample irradiated at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, which exhibited intermediate slope values (132 mN/nm for Berkovich and 6 mN/nm for spherical). These findings underscore the critical role of irradiation temperature in governing the accumulation and evolution of irradiation-induced defect structures, which in turn affect the elastic and mechanical response of structural materials considered for nuclear environments.

It is known that the elastic part of the load–displacement curves can be fitted with the Hertz model for isotropic elastic contact. Therefore, the Hertz contact theory provides a relationship between the applied load (P) and the resulting indentation depth (h) as [45]:

$$P = \frac{4}{3} E_r \sqrt{R} h^{3/2}$$

In this framework, the shear stress, τ , in the material at the elastic loading regime can be computed as follows [45]:

$$\tau = 0.31 \left(\frac{6PE_r^2}{\pi^3 R^2} \right)^{1/3}$$

where P is the load, E_r the reduced modulus, and R the tip radius. Using this formula, we calculated the maximum shear stress and represented the results in Fig. 7 and Table 4.

When comparing the radii of the indenters, significant differences in the calculated shear stresses are observed. As shown in Fig. 7, the calculated shear stresses for the Berkovich indenter tip (black dots) are notably higher than those for the spherical indenters (red dots). The critical shear stress required for homogeneous dislocation nucleation in crystalline metals typically ranges from $G/5$ to $G/30$ [28], where G represents the shear modulus. For Fe-9Cr alloy, with a shear modulus of 84 GPa [16], the critical shear stress is expected to fall between 2.8 GPa and 16.8 GPa. While the calculated shear stress for the Berkovich tip falls within this range, the values for the spherical indenter are lower which can be attributed to the well-documented Indentation Size Effect (ISE) [28,46].

Although the ISE is generally more pronounced in Berkovich indentation due to its sharp geometry and confined plastic zone, the measured shear stress in this case primarily reflects the critical stress required for dislocation nucleation. This localized plasticity response is highly sensitive to the presence of irradiation-induced defects and therefore provides insight into the intrinsic mechanical behavior of the irradiated ferritic matrix. In contrast, the 5 μm spherical indenter induces a broader and deeper plastic zone, where plastic flow involves a greater volume of material and is more influenced by heterogeneity in the defect structure. While the influence of ISE is reduced in the spherical geometry, this is compensated by the increased role of defect–dislocation interactions, which tend to lower the apparent stress

Fig. 7. Cross-sectional STEM images of the a-b) pristine and self-irradiated Fe-9Cr alloy to a damage level of 5 dpa at room temperature (RT) (c-e) and at 300 °C (f-h).

Table 4

Average shear stress calculated for every indenter and sample.

		Average shear stress (GPa)				
Sample	pristine	pristine	5dpa RT	1dpa	5dpa	
Tip	RT	annealed 300 °C	300 °C	300 °C	300 °C	
Berkovich	9.59	9.13±0.99	9.16	8.24	9.24	
tip	±1.32		±1.13	±0.80	±1.14	
5 μm tip	2.40	1.88±0.89	2.20	2.97	3.34	
	±0.43		±0.27	±0.41	±1.42	

values.

The divergence between results obtained with Berkovich and spherical tips highlights the scale-dependent nature of irradiation effects. Localized measurements reveal a potential softening behavior associated with facilitated dislocation nucleation at defect sites, whereas bulk-scale measurements indicate irradiation-induced hardening due to

the accumulation of defects that impede dislocation motion. These contrasting responses underscore the importance of employing complementary indentation techniques to fully characterize the complex interplay between irradiation damage and plastic deformation mechanisms in structural materials exposed to extreme environments.

Interpretation of these results must also account for the differences in stress distribution and activated deformation mechanisms imposed by the indenter geometry. The sharp Berkovich tip generates high local stresses within a confined plastic zone, resulting in dislocation nucleation and shear stress values that approximate the intrinsic critical resolved shear stress. In contrast, the spherical indenter activates plastic flow over a broader and deeper volume, where defect–dislocation interactions dominate. As a result, the measured shear stress is lower not because of a reduced intrinsic strength, but due to the higher probability of encountering irradiation-induced obstacles that facilitate dislocation motion. Thus, Berkovich indentation captures nucleation-controlled

responses, while spherical indentation probes bulk-like plastic resistance shaped by irradiation-induced microstructural heterogeneity.

3.2. Microstructure characterization

The TEM technique was used for the microstructural investigations of irradiation defects in the studied materials. The samples were tilted to the $\langle 111 \rangle$ zone axis and then to $g=110$. Fig. 7 shows BF-STEM images acquired from the samples annealed at 300 °C (a-b) irradiated up to 5 dpa at RT (c-e) and 300 °C (f-h). Ion irradiation has been reported to induce the formation of band-like microstructures [40]. As shown in Fig. 7c and 7f, three distinct bands can be identified. The first band, near the surface, exhibits an increasing number and size of dislocation loops. The second band contains dislocation loops connected to injected interstitials, while the third corresponds to the non-irradiated region.

The density of dislocation lines (marked with white arrows in Fig. 7 in the irradiated ($3.22 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$) and non-irradiated ($2.76 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$) regions, as shown in Fig. 7c, is comparable. A similar observation is made in Fig. 7f, where the dislocation lines density in the irradiated region is $1.54 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$, while in the non-irradiated region, it is $1.71 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$. This suggests that these dislocations preexisted in the material prior to ion irradiation. Such dislocations are commonly found in metallic materials, and their density is associated with the material's thermo-mechanical history [2].

In this study, the region extending from the surface to the damage peak is of primary interest (see Fig. 4). A comparison of the Fe-9Cr alloy irradiated at room temperature (RT) (Fig. 7c) and at 300 °C (Fig. 7f) up to 5 dpa reveals significant differences in defect structures. In the RT-irradiated sample, ion irradiation results in the formation of a high density of uniformly distributed fine dislocation loops (yellow arrows) within the matrix, ranging in size from 2 to 10 nm. These loops appear as black dots in STEM images. Similar defects are commonly observed in structural materials subjected to ion and neutron and proton irradiation [47–54]. At room temperature, irradiation-induced defects remain more static, preventing the formation of complex dislocation networks. As a result, RT-irradiated samples contain a higher density of isolated dislocation loops, which contribute to more significant hardening. This increased defect density raises the stress required for the initiation of plastic deformation, leading to a higher critical load for the onset of a pop-in event during nanoindentation, as observed with both the Berkovich (Fig. 5c) and spherical (Fig. 6c) tips.

In contrast, the sample irradiated at 300 °C exhibits a matrix free of small dislocation loops. Instead, small dislocation loops tend to agglomerate around pre-existing large dislocation lines (see Fig. 7f-h), a phenomenon known as dislocation decoration. This effect has been previously observed in various neutron- and heavy ion-irradiated alloys [55]. Hernández-Mayoral et al. [56] reported that in neutron-irradiated Fe-Cr alloys (300 °C, Cr > 5 %), fine dislocation loops preferentially decorate pre-existing dislocation lines. Trinkaus et al. [57] attributed this behavior to the trapping of mobile dislocation loops by the local strain fields generated by these dislocation lines, which act as pinning sites and hinder further dislocation mobility. Additionally, Terentyev et al. [58] observed that Cr has a strong affinity for $\frac{1}{2}\langle 111 \rangle$ interstitial clusters, suggesting that the structures in Fig. 7f may correspond to $\frac{1}{2}\langle 111 \rangle$ interstitial-type loops with locally elevated Cr content. In-situ TEM experiments on Fe-Cr alloys further indicate that Cr segregation at the periphery of $\frac{1}{2}\langle 111 \rangle$ interstitial loops significantly reduces their mobility compared to pure Fe [59]. This stabilization effect contributes to irradiation-induced hardening by restricting defect dynamics and impeding plastic deformation.

Importantly, this dislocation decoration effect is absent in the unirradiated material annealed at 300 °C, where the dislocation structure remains free of such loop agglomeration. This key difference indicates that the observed loop - dislocation interaction is a direct consequence of high-temperature ion irradiation and not an intrinsic microstructural feature. The presence of such decorated structures thus highlights the

significant role of irradiation conditions - particularly temperature and Cr content—in shaping the defect landscape and mechanical behavior of Fe-Cr alloys.

Finally, Fig. 7g highlights the presence of helical dislocations (green arrows), which provide further insight into the high-temperature microstructural evolution [60,61]. Helical dislocations form when mobile dislocation loops interact with pre-existing dislocations in a manner that results in non-conservative climb, a mechanism where dislocations absorb or emit point defects (interstitials or vacancies) under irradiation. This process causes the dislocation line to develop a spiral or helical shape, as observed in the high-magnification image, see Fig. 7g. The formation of these helical structures suggests that at higher temperatures, defect mobility and dynamic recovery mechanisms become more prominent. These structures suggest that the material experiences a degree of self-recovery, reducing the density of freely distributed irradiation defects. Consequently, the stress required for the onset of plastic deformation is lower, leading to an earlier pop-in event (lower pop-in load) compared to RT-irradiated samples (see Table 4).

4. Discussion

The nanoindentation results clearly demonstrate the Indentation Size Effect (ISE), where shear stress decreases as the indenter radius increases. This phenomenon occurs because a larger indenter has a higher probability of encountering pre-existing dislocations when loading. Using a small indenter, such as a Berkovich, increases the likelihood of probing a volume of material without pre-existing dislocations. This leads to plastic deformation only after reaching the theoretical stress threshold and nucleating new dislocations. Conversely, a larger indenter increases the chance of encountering pre-existing dislocations, which aid in initiating plasticity [28,33,46,62,63].

In the case of the Berkovich indenter tip, the shear stresses measured in unirradiated materials closely match the theoretical shear stress. This is due to the sharp geometry of the indenter, which probes a relatively defect-free volume at shallow depths (~15 nm), minimizing the influence of pre-existing dislocations due to the highly localized stress fields. However, in samples irradiated up to 1 dpa, a noticeable decrease in shear stress is observed. This reduction can be explained by the introduction of irradiation-induced defects. At low dpa, irradiation generates point defects which initially reduce the resistance to dislocation motion by acting as weak obstacles or inducing localized stress relaxation, thereby lowering the required shear stress [64,65]. For the spherical tip, measurements of shear stress are significantly lower than those for the Berkovich tip (see Fig. 8). This suggests that the dislocation nucleation sources probed during indentation with larger tips require lower energy

Fig. 8. The maximum shear stress under a) Berkovich tip, b) 5 μm tip for all samples.

to activate than those from irradiation-induced defects.

The ion irradiation process introduces a significant number of defects to the microstructure, such as dislocation loops and segregation of atoms (especially at the grain boundaries, which often occur at high temperatures [2,20,66,67]). These defects act as obstacles to dislocation movement, requiring a higher applied load to overcome them and initiate plastic deformation. These dislocation loops can interact with dislocation lines, increasing the resistance to dislocation motion and, consequently, the shear stress needed for plastic deformation. During the ion irradiation process, carbon atoms or other solute atoms can diffuse into stress fields around existing dislocations, forming a Cottrell atmosphere and subsequently pinning the dislocations [68–70]. Additionally, while nanoindentation pop-ins and yield drops during tensile testing occur at different length scales, they both represent manifestations of strain softening and may have a fundamental relationship. Dislocations trapped by solute atmospheres can break free at the upper yield point, resulting in instantaneous softening and a sharp drop in yield strength. As the load is released and the specimen undergoes a dwell period, solute atoms diffuse to the dislocations, decreasing the mobile dislocation density and causing the reappearance of the yield point, a phenomenon known as strain aging [70].

The structural components of Gen. IV and fusion reactors will be subjected to extremely harsh operating conditions – high temperatures combined with severe neutron irradiation. This may lead to the degradation of their performance due to the accumulation of radiation-induced defects. Therefore, understanding the phenomenon of radiation hardening at a fundamental level is essential for the development of radiation-resistant materials for applications in future fission and fusion reactors. The present study investigates this phenomenon in the Fe-9Cr alloy, which serves as a model alloy in the design of ferritic/martensitic

steels for the nuclear industry. Understanding irradiation hardening requires not only determining how irradiation-induced defect formation affects mechanical properties but also clarifying how these defects influence the dynamics of dislocations generated during deformation. This effect is illustrated in Fig. 9, which presents TEM images acquired from areas beneath the indenter tip in the studied Fe-9Cr alloy in three different states: pristine, and implanted up to 5 dpa at RT and 300 °C. In each state, a high density of tangled dislocation lines was observed; however, a closer examination reveals significant differences between the samples.

In the pristine Fe-9Cr alloy, nanoindentation produces a well-defined deformation zone with an elevated density of dislocation lines, primarily activated along {011} slip planes [71]. Due to the low initial defect density, dislocations generated during indentation move with minimal obstruction, requiring relatively low stress to initiate plasticity. As a result, the first pop-in event occurs at a lower critical stress, as shown in Fig. 5. Fig. 9a provides an overview of the indentation-affected region, displaying an extensive network of dislocation lines. Within this plastic deformation zone, slip bands and dislocation tangles emerge in response to the applied stress. A specific area of interest is highlighted by a boxed region, which is further examined at higher magnification in Fig. 9d.

Following ion irradiation, significant changes in the dislocation structure occur, as illustrated in Fig. 9b. Unlike the pristine material, where dislocation motion is relatively unimpeded, the room-temperature irradiated Fe-9Cr alloy exhibits a high density of small dislocation loops distributed throughout the microstructure. These irradiation-induced defects act as obstacles to dislocation glide, either by direct physical interactions or through their associated elastic stress fields, resulting in significant pinning of mobile dislocations. An example of such an interaction between irradiation-induced dislocation

Fig. 9. Cross-sectional STEM images of the plastically deformed regions beneath the indenter tip in pristine Fe-9Cr (a), and in self-irradiated Fe-9Cr to a damage level of 5 dpa at RT (b) and at 300 °C (c).

loops and the dislocation line is shown in the red box in Fig. 9e. Consequently, plastic deformation proceeds via the nucleation of new dislocations rather than the movement of pre-existing ones. As a result, the irradiated microstructure develops a tangled, forest-like dislocation network. Fig. 9e provides a more detailed view, where yellow arrows indicate larger dislocation loops, while purple arrows highlight regions of intense dislocation interactions, likely due to cross-slip or pile-ups. This increased dislocation entanglement leads to a higher critical stress required for plasticity initiation, consistent with the elevated pop-in loads observed in Fig. 5 [42,72].

Fig. 9c illustrates the dislocation structure beneath the indent in a sample irradiated to 5 dpa at 300 °C. Compared to both the pristine and RT-irradiated samples, this microstructure exhibits distinct deformation behavior. Considering the results obtained from nanoindentation analysis, the critical stress for the first pop-in event is significantly lower than in the RT-irradiated sample, as shown in Fig. 5. This reduction in pop-in stress is closely linked to irradiation-induced modifications in the defect structure. At 300 °C, irradiation leads to the preferential formation of dislocation loops near pre-existing dislocation lines, while the surrounding matrix remains relatively free of defects, as shown in Fig. 8d. This microstructural configuration facilitates the formation of dislocation channels, enabling more efficient dislocation glide. As a result, the overall density of dislocation lines beneath the indenter is significantly lower than in the RT-irradiated sample, and dislocation tangling is noticeably reduced. Fig. 9f provides a magnified view of the boxed region in Fig. 9c, emphasizing key microstructural features. The purple arrows indicate mobile dislocation segments, whereas the yellow arrows highlight defect sites that act as pinning points. Despite the enhanced dislocation mobility in these channels, the critical stress for the pop-in event remains higher than in the pristine sample [42].

The increased pop-in stress in the irradiated material can be attributed to the presence of irradiation-induced dislocation loops, which serve as strong barriers to dislocation motion. Unlike in the pristine material, where dislocations move relatively freely, these loops effectively pin dislocations, limiting their mobility and altering the deformation mechanism. As a result, a significant increase in the pop-in was observed for the RT irradiated sample due to the occurrence of high density of fine dislocation loops. These loops block the motion of the pre-existing dislocations in the material, resulting in the nucleation of new dislocations to accommodate the strain induced by the indenter. However, the newly formed dislocations also interact with the loops, drastically increasing their density (Fig. 10) and leading to significant hardening. On the other hand, slightly different mechanisms were observed during the irradiation at the intermediate temperatures (300 °C). In this case, the accumulation of dislocation loops near pre-existing dislocation lines results in the formation of loop-depleted channels along these lines, where dislocation slip can occur with relatively lower resistance. However, the immobility of pre-existing dislocations, combined with the obstruction of newly formed dislocations by the dislocation line-loop structures, still leads to increased pop-in stress compared to the pristine sample. Furthermore, these loops may be also decorated with Cr atoms, which diffuse into their vicinity during irradiation, as previously reported in the literature [67,73,74]. This Cr segregation stabilizes the loops, making them more resistant to annihilation or bypassing by moving dislocations. As a result, pre-existing dislocations in the irradiated material cannot contribute effectively to plastic deformation. Instead, new dislocations must nucleate to accommodate the applied stress, increasing the threshold stress required for the pop-in event. This effect may be further enhanced by radiation-induced segregation (RIS), a phenomenon previously reported in Fe-Cr alloys [17,67,73,75,76].

5. Conclusion

This study investigates the influence of ion irradiation on the deformation behavior of Fe-9Cr alloys by employing two different tip

Fig. 10. Dislocation density beneath the indent at a depth of approximately 500 nm in pristine and irradiated samples (up to 5 dpa) at RT and 300 °C.

geometries to distinguish differences in the pop-in shear stress required to initiate plasticity. Nanoindentation was used as a sensitive tool to assess irradiation-induced changes in mechanical properties, revealing how microstructural alterations from irradiation affect dislocation nucleation and mobility.

Our findings demonstrate that ion irradiation significantly modifies the plastic deformation mechanisms. Room-temperature irradiation results in a high density of uniformly distributed fine dislocation loops, which act as strong obstacles to dislocation motion. This leads to pronounced hardening and an increased critical stress for the onset of plasticity. In contrast, irradiation at 300 °C promotes the formation of dislocation channels through loop agglomeration along pre-existing dislocations, reducing matrix defect density and lowering the pop-in stress compared to room-temperature irradiation.

The possible segregation of chromium at irradiation-induced defects may further stabilize these dislocation loops, enhancing their resistance to shearing and contributing to the increased pop-in stresses. These results highlight the complex interplay between irradiation damage, solute segregation, and dislocation dynamics.

The observed differences in measured shear stress using Berkovich and spherical indenters-attributed to their interaction with pre-existing versus nearly defect-free regions-underline the importance of tip geometry in interpreting nanoindentation data. However, the key contribution of this work lies in demonstrating the capability of nanoindentation to probe irradiation-induced changes in deformation behavior, with important implications for the design of radiation-resistant materials in nuclear applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

K. Mulewska: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **D. Kalita:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **M. Wilczopolska:** Investigation. **W. Chromiński:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **P.A. Ferreirós:** Investigation. **Ł. Kurpaska:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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